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Right Deprivation in the Legal Regulation Mechanism of Civil Property Relations

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Abstract

The study examines aspects of how deprivation of a civil right forms when such rights can determine a possible decrease in quality of life. Authors explore this problem in accordance with provisions of the civil legislation and form practical means for application of the right deprivation mechanism based on the analysis of international legislations. In particular, possibilities of estate seizures and gradual transformation of formalized law space into doctrinal subsystems are analyzed. The work investigates the possibility to use measures of both state and private influence in this field and presents prognostic components that can affect regulation variations of estate seizure of estates based on an agreed-upon procedure between states. A different procedure is proposed for joint ownership and realization of a provision on managing land and ecological legislations as a field of civil relations. The practical aim of the work can be applied to solving disputes regarding the need for joint regulation of civil property relations in international and local civil law. Measures that determine the possibility for structural and comprehensive informing of certain forms and structures of legal science are implemented.

Keywords

Property Relations, Regulation, Right Deprivation Mechanism, Formalization, Field of Land Law.

Introduction

In the science of land law, scientists identify a special kind of legal relations-land procedural legal relations-meaning such that regulate norms, establish an order of creation, change or termination of land legal relations. This position regarding the inclusion of subjects that, according to land legislation, are not direct participants in land legal relations but without their involvement the realization of legal provision regarding compulsory acquisition. These subjects are courts, some specific state agencies (enforcement agencies, internal affairs agencies, military or emergency management agencies, etc.). In our opinion, the main criteria regarding the possibility of including into the list of subjects the corresponding legal relations are a direct participation of a corresponding agency or a physical, legal party and the existence of their interest in exercising compulsory acquisition. Assuming that the discussed state agencies are exercising a direct acquisition benefiting the state and are interested in executing functions of direct acquisition imposed upon them by the legislation, they can be categorized as subjects of the studied legal relations. The involvement of courts in the studied legal relations is instrumental since it is courts that sanction decision about a possibility of compulsory acquisition of an estate in most cases (Kostruba, 2017). These considerations justify the inclusion of courts as subjects of legal relations of compulsory acquisition of estates.

In a state and law theory, the content of legal relations is understood as rights and obligations of their participants. Therefore, the content of the studied legal relation can be considered rights and obligations of subjects regarding compulsory transition of a right to an estate. The structure of the content can be simple (subjective law and legal responsibility) and complex (for public officials-authority, legal responsibility). While subjective law is understood as provided and protected by state extent (limit) of the possible (permitted) behavior of an individual towards the satisfaction of their legal interests that are envisaged by objective law. Unlike objective law, which acts as a total or a system of existing legal norms, subjective law acts as law that belongs only to a specific subject and is realized solely by the expression of the will of this individual.

When describing the content of studied legal relations based on these attributes, the following should be noted. Participants enter the corresponding legal relations not voluntarily. The reason for their participation in legal relations can be different-unlawful behavior (crime, offence or civil violation), not reaching an agreement with state agencies or local administration concerning a voluntary acquisition of an estate or other causes. In our opinion, this reason causes existing domination of legal responsibilities of subjects of legal relations over their subjective rights. Subjective behavior of state agencies and their public officials is strictly limited by the authority provided to them in accordance with the current legislation. Only strict abidance to law and acting within specific boundaries allows self to acknowledge the process of compulsory acquisition of an estate as legitimate. At the same time, during specific stages of compulsory acquisition, law provides an individual with several possible variants of its behavior (legal content), such as the possibility to accept a compensation offer for an estate or provision of another estate in exchange for the one being acquired. Nevertheless, the real behavior of an individual (factual content) allows us to make conclusions that in such case an individual does not use granted to him subjective rights, which is followed by their legal responsibility to participate in studied legal relations (Ushakov et al., 2017).

Legal regulation of compulsory acquisition of estates should be examined starting from a number of sources of law and their influence on regulation. Besides the fact that the modern law study differentiates the following main forms of sources of law: normative-legal act, normative legal agreement, legal precedent, legal custom, authorities, authors consider application of legal customs in the sphere of compulsory acquisition of estates impossible due to the following. Constitutions of most countries state that the right of ownership over land is acquired and realized by citizens, legal parties and the state only in accordance with law. Additionally, the order and foundation of compulsory deprivation of ownership rights can be established only by law. Therefore, it is impossible to apply legal customs in the sphere of compulsory acquisition of estates (Lukyanova, 2014; Lukyanova et al., 2017; Rath and Lee, 2018).

Literature Review

In Roman law, "acquisition" was called "any act which transferred the ownership right". Pomponius stated in his works that during acquisition we transfer to someone else the property with a condition that property would be in if it still was ours, and that is the course for all civil law (Welshman, 1995). Simmons wrote that acquisition in its narrow sense is termination of an ownership right through its transfer to another person, and, therefore, it is only subjectively a termination of a right, meaning that it's a termination for this person, while objectively acquired right continues to exist for another person with the same content and the same specifics that distinguished it before an acquisition act (Simmons, 1995). MacKlin reached this conclusion when analyzing methods of establishing subjective rights in civil law (MacKlin, 1993). It is worth noting that Alcantara is not the only representative of the pre-revolutionary civil law who gave attention to the essence of acquisitions (Alcantara, 1996). This question received a deep comprehension in the work of Bradford where the author analyzes different methods of termination and forfeiture of an ownership right (Bradford, 2005). Meanwhile, one researcher notes that acquisition can be viewed both in its wide and narrow senses (Arya, 2006). In its wide sense-it is a loss of an ownership right. In its narrow sense-it is a voluntary transfer of ownership rights from one person to another. This way, according to the narrow (immediate) understanding, the latter is a voluntary legal act, which must result in a transfer of rights to another person, and as a result, the previous owner loses this right (Ellerman, 2010). The emphasis on the voluntary nature of acquisition is not random since the author clearly understood that this act is based on a voluntary expression of will of a rights-holder. Though later in the text, the author uses the term "acquisition" to denote compulsory transfer of rights on the basis of confiscation and expropriation. These cases he calls "compulsory acquisition", which is performed independently from the will of a rights-holder (Murray, 2014).

When analyzing the current legislation, Duncanson identifies such forms of usage and understanding of the term "acquisition": "acquisition" is used as an ancestral category to signify the whole of transition (transfer) mechanism of property (rights) from one party to another at the discretion of an owner or holder; "acquisition" can be used as a category of types, more specifically as one of the reasons to terminate an ownership right, and in such understanding it should be determined in a way where the owner of an item (property) on at their own discretion performs a transfer of an item (ownership right) to another person (Duncanson, 2009).

Methodology

The work uses the method of legal analysis since the main doctrinal understanding is based on the possibility to predict legal construction by the qualitative content of legal acts.

The development of legal regulation of any state institution is unimaginable without considering international legal norms in the form of international principles, agreements and recommendations. International law provides modern global rule of law, has a deep influence in the system of its norms, directs the development of domestic national law, acts as criteria for the lawfulness of state's behavior on an international level and in an internal sphere of social-legal relations. The existence of international conventions, double-sided and many-sided agreements, creation of non-governmental human rights bodies determine harmonization and unification of national legal systems of different countries. This is why when advancing legal institutions of any country it is necessary to take into account international legal principles and norms, as well as their practices in certain countries (Lerat, 2013; Baynova et al., 2016).

The institute of compulsory acquisition of estates is familiar to legislations of all countries in different forms. As a rule, common international approach regarding compulsory acquisition of objects of private ownership rights by governments is based on recognition of every state's sovereignty on its territory, the existence of specific exclusive law that determines the character and content of ownership rights, also establishment of a specific order concerning its purchase, transition or forfeiture.

Results And Discussion

A specific unification of order of exercising such compulsory acquisition and establishment of specific guideline list of reasons for the acquisition. According to Protocol 1 article 1 of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950, no one shall be deprived of his possessions except in the public interest and subject to the conditions provided for by law and by the general principles of international law. Among the instruments the state uses to perform compulsory acquisition of estates and specific international-legal doctrines, there are expropriation, repurchase and compulsory acquisition in the public interest, confiscation, requisition and nationalization (Brown & Marusek, 2014).

One of the oldest ways of compulsory acquisition of property is requisition, which in its earliest form was known as "military" requisition. In the ancient times, it was considered a common rule that local population has to supply the army with resources. In the Middle Ages and up to the Thirty Year's War, there was a custom of virtually total unlimited pillage of property of population in an army-occupied region. The beginning of more or less correct regulation was laid down by Gustaf VI Adolf who shifted the responsibility of gathering supplies on special officers whose responsibility was to deliver collected supplies to owners of houses where soldiers stationed. This system received a significant improvement during the Revolutionary Wars. After the French Revolution, requisition started to apply to the property of their own subjects. Under provision "Field army operations" of 1890, requisition was the only way to satisfy the needs of army when other, normal ways were either non-feasible or would be unsuccessful.

International regulation of requisition was reflected in article 52 of the Convention respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land of 1907, which states that requisition can be performed for the needs of the army of occupation and cannot be performed to satisfy the needs of a warring country. Unauthorized requisition performed by soldiers or officers is unlawful. Requisition is only allowed in proportion to the military needs, and it should be repaid in cash; if not-requisition has to be affirmed by a receipt and repaid as soon as possible. The Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War of 12 August 1949 contains similar provisions. These conventions establish that requisitions measures regarding specific property can be requisitioned by a belligerent in such cases and to the extent when it is absolutely necessary (article 19 of the Convention respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land of 18 October 1907) and only if the requirements of the civilian population have been taken into account (article 55 of the Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War). Common requirements for compensation are established. According to a complex analysis of the specified conventions, the term requisition does not include the ability for compulsory acquisition of estates but only of movable property and property of the highest necessity (the occupying power can requisition only foodstuffs, articles or medical supplies...; the occupying power can requisition civilian hospitals only temporarily and only in cases of urgent necessity...; requisition in kind and services can only be demanded for the needs of the army of occupation...; an army of occupation can only take possession of cash, funds, and realizable securities, which are strictly the property of the State, depots of arms, means of transport, stores and supplies, and, generally, all movable property belonging to the State which may be used for military operations, etc.). As a confirmation that requisition of estates was not present in the international practice, article 55 of the Convention respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land states that the occupying State shall be regarded only as administrator and usufructuary of public buildings, real estate, forests, and agricultural estates belonging to the hostile State, and situated in the occupied country. It must safeguard the capital of these properties, and administer them in accordance with the rules of usufruct (Akkhat, 2015).

In addition to military requisition, the notion of peacetime requisition formed much later. International-legal regulation considers "peacetime" requisition only as prohibition with a reservation concerning specific exceptions (McGillcuddy, 2012). A single approach was developed for them, which consisted of establishing responsibilities of states where exceptional circumstances has formed, in response to which measures of compulsory acquisition were executed, while owners would be compensated under the corresponding legal regime (national or the most favorable one), which corresponded with general principles of international law regarding legal equity and non-discrimination. An example of the prohibition can provisions of the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations of 1961, which forbid requisition of property (including estates) of diplomatic and consular agencies in during peace or war time.

When analyzing legislations of different countries, it should be noted that usually requisition is included in the list of compulsory acquisition. When researching norms of foreign countries, the following qualities should be noted: in legislation of a number of countries, the notion of exclusively military requisition (generally, this involves only countries of Anglo-Saxon law; "peacetime" requisition is considered as compulsory acquisition of property (including estates) only in time of emergencies (natural disasters, epidemics, epizootics, etc.); a good example is CIS countries (Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, Moldova, Uzbekistan, etc.); military requisition in national law, as opposed to international norms, is understood as provision of personal national defense interests and not as satisfaction of needs of occupational armies; national requisition, unlike international principles, allows compulsory acquisition of real property, including estates; requisition outlines a simplified procedure of compulsory acquisition, in comparison to other reasons (generally, it is immediate acquisition without the participation of court bodies in assessing the necessity of this acquisition); certain states often establish special guarantees in relation to requisition-for example, the right of successors to receive repayment (compensation) for requisition of their property is protected (in the Republic of Kazakhstan) (Cheng, 2008).

A different quality of requisitions is the existence of its specific types. For example, Russian legislation distinguishes two types of requisition: permanent and temporary. Except that estates can be requisitioned only temporarily. According to article 51 of the Land Code of the Russian Federation, during natural disaster, accidents, epidemics, epizootics or other circumstances that are of urgent matter, estate can be temporarily seized from its owners by authorized executive state bodies in order to protect vital interests of citizens, society and state from threats, caused by these emergencies, with due compensation of incurred damages and a document of requisition and return given to the owner of the estate after disposal. If it is impossible to dispose of hazardous effects, the estate is either acquired or exchanged for an equivalent one. When the estate is transferred to land reserves or land freeze, its further use is determined by the Government of the Russian Federation. Besides the Russian Federation, the institute of temporary requisition is also used in Italy (Howard-Hassmann, 2004).

In the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, the term "confiscation" is explained as the permanent deprivation of property by order of a court or other competent authority. The term "property" means assets of every kind, whether corporeal or incorporeal, movable or immovable, tangible or intangible, and legal documents or instruments evidencing title to, or interest in, such assets. The content of international-legal norms allows confiscation of property that was involved in a crime that is a special confiscation. The norms of these conventions do not contain a provision clarifying the question about confiscation of estates (that is do they allow or limit such confiscation) (Bales & Robbins, 2011).

Legal systems of many countries include another type of confiscation-general, which involves acquisition of all property, regardless of their relation to the crime committed. Depending on which type of confiscation the state penal system establishes-general or special, countries can be divided into three groups. The first group recognizes only general confiscation as punishment, that is the compulsory non-repayable conversion of a convicted offender's property, which was not connected in any way to a crime committed, to the benefit of a state (Belarus, Bulgaria, Vietnam, Denmark, Kazakhstan, China, Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Cuba, Laos, Latvia, Mauritania, Madagascar, Mongolia, Sudan, Tajikistan, Togo, Ethiopia, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan abolished general confiscation in 2001, Russia in 2003).

Legislations of the second group of countries allow special confiscation as punishment-compulsory non-repayable seizure of specific types of property, which were otherwise (directly or indirectly) connected to a crime committed by a convicted person (objects of crime, instruments and means of committing a crime, property obtained through crime, dangerous or harmful objects, etc.), executed by a special law and to the benefit of a state. Punishment in the form of special confiscation of property is covered in legislations of such countries as the Republic of Korea, the Netherlands, Japan, etc. The third group of states has two types of confiscation-established-general and special. Such countries include, in particular, France and Ukraine.

It is worth noting that some countries have fully or partially abandoned such an institute of criminal law as confiscation of property. A number of countries have placed a prohibition on the application of general confiscation in their constitutions (Azerbaijan, Argentina, Barbados, Bahrain, Belgium, Cyprus, Colombia, Costa Rica, Lebanon, Malaysia, Maldives, Mexico, Nicaragua, UAE, Paraguay, Romania, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Chile, etc.) Such prohibition is justified by the fact that confiscation of property results in almost complete material insecurity not only for the convict but also their family, a substantial psychological impact on these individuals, which do not correspond with the goals of punishment. In addition, such measures violate the rights and freedoms of citizens and are an obstacle to humanization and liberalization of criminal law. The legislation of the Republic of Georgia recognizes any confiscation of property as an anti-constitutional norm and is excluded from provisions of the Criminal Code because of violation of the principle of obligatory equivalent compensation for the acquisition of private property.

In many countries, where general confiscation persists, its application is often limited since this measure has a very significant impact on the living conditions of not only the convicted person but also their family. In France, for example, it can only be used for crimes against humanity, as well as illegal production, import and export of drugs. In Belarus and Tajikistan, it can be imposed only for grave and particularly grave crimes committed for financial gain, in cases envisaged by the special part of the Criminal Code. In Kazakhstan, confiscation can be imposed only for profit-motivated crimes.

Special attention should be paid to the list of property that is not subject to confiscation and does not include estates in it. As a general rule, the list includes the property necessary for living of a convicted person or individuals who are such person's dependent, joint housing, estates, furniture, clothes, children's items, etc. The types of property that can be confiscated are often largely the same in different countries. Returning to the issue of estate confiscation, it should be noted that a number of countries prohibit confiscation of estates. For example, according to a list of property that is not subject to confiscation by the verdict given in the annex to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus, confiscation is not applicable to estates on which the house and outbuildings are located, as well as estates required for agricultural or subsidiary economy (McGillcuddy, 2012).

Of interest to us is the application of expropriation in international law. In its broadest sense, expropriation means any compulsory acquisition of property, which includes military, state or public interests, nationalization and confiscation. Nevertheless, a number of scientists disagree with this understanding of expropriation: some scholars note that expropriation is the exclusively paid (compensatory) acquisition of an object, another group notes the unpaid nature of expropriation, and some believe that expropriation is solely the acquisition of property (sometimes-only estates and real property located on them) for public purposes that are not related to emergencies. Presumably, this situation arose primarily because of the lack of a single international legal terminology in this sphere. Thus, we can find similar definitions of expropriation in foreign countries: "eminent domain" (United States of America, Philippines), "compulsory purchase" (Great Britain, New Zealand, Ireland), "resumption" (Hong Kong), "resumption/compulsory acquisition" (Australia), "expropriation" (South Africa, Canada), "alienation of land for (state) public needs (public necessity)" (Ukraine, Russia). The CIS countries do not use the term "expropriation" in their legislations (with the exception of the Republic of Moldova-article 94 of the Land Code states that conditions and procedure of expropriation for state or public needs of land and construction objects, owned by physical and legal parties, are regulated by the special legislation), although, these countries often use the studied term within international legal agreements. This also creates additional disagreements in the correct understanding of this institution. Complex international legal documents do not use special terminology (for example, article 1 of the Protocol No. 1 to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950, they only contain a rule that the private owner cannot be deprived of property, except in the public interest. Despite inconsistencies in international legal and national approaches to understanding of expropriation, the unifying factor is that expropriation is understood as the compulsory acquisition specifically of estates (Doupe & Salter, 2000).

A normative rule about the non-discriminatory nature of provisions regulating property of private owners is contained in constitutions of most countries of the world in general forms. More detailed principles and provisions concerning compulsory acquisition of estates and the issue of compensation to owners of acquired estates are defined in separate laws. In foreign countries, compulsory acquisition of estates is regulated by a number of normative-legal acts, based on the following principles: clearly defined public needs or emergencies; the need for just and full reimbursement to the owners of expropriated estates; designation of procedural rights of the parties concerned, including a preliminary notice, the right to just compensation and the right to appeal; court hearing of compensatory offers if there are any procedural violations, abuses, etc. As a rule, these principles and provisions concerning compulsory acquisition of estates and the issue of compensation to owners of acquired estates are defined in separate laws (Anderson, 2014).

The Constitution of the Kingdom of Norway is the oldest one in Europe-adopted back in the early nineteenth century (May 17, 1814), it is still in continuous force, having undergone significant changes in the course of constitutional reforms. However, some of its provisions have been retained from its first edition to this day. Such provisions include § 104, which envisages that the right to immovable and movable property cannot be violated in any way, and § 105, according to which, if for reasons of state necessity any property is to be conceded into public use, the owner receives a full reimbursement from state treasury.

In the Constitution of the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg of 17 October 1868 (as amended), article 16 states:

"No one shall be deprived of their property except in the public interest and in the manner prescribed by law, and subject to fair and prior compensation".

In the 19th century, the theory of the social function of property got widespread use in Europe, whose ideas are incorporated in constitutional approaches to regulation of property relations, includes compulsory acquisition of private property. The theory of the social function of property, according to which subjects of property rights are obliged to obey social norms and fulfill social functions assigned to them, was enthusiastically received by western legislators. At the same time, scientists expressed the opinion that elements of such ideas were usually included in the constitution, which arose on the wave of popular speeches and resolutions.

One of the first European constitutions that incorporated a new approach to the recognition of the social function of private property was Germany's Weimar Constitution of 1919. It established private property as "social duty". Compulsory acquisition of property was allowed only for the needs of society, on legal grounds and for an appropriate reimbursement (Fox, 2000).

Of particular interest is France, whose legal development is historically linked to the beginning of the formation of its institutions. The Declaration of the French Republic of 4 October 1788 reserves attention to a crime committed by a convicted person (objects of crime, instruments and means of committing a crime, property obtained through crime, dangerous or harmful objects, etc.), executed by a special law and to the benefit of a state. Punishment in the form of special confiscation of property is covered in legislations of such countries as the Republic of Korea, the Netherlands, Japan, etc. The third group of states has two types of confiscation-established-general and special. Such countries include, in particular, France and Ukraine.

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In many countries, where general confiscation persists, its application is often limited since this measure has a very significant impact on the living conditions of not only the convicted person but also their family. In France, for example, it can only be used for crimes against humanity, as well as illegal production, import and export of drugs. In Belarus and Tajikistan, it can be imposed only for grave and particularly grave crimes committed for financial gain, in cases envisaged by the special part of the Criminal Code. In Kazakhstan, confiscation can be imposed only for profit-motivated crimes.

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Of interest to us is the application of expropriation in international law. In its broadest sense, expropriation means any compulsory acquisition of property, which includes military, state or public interests, nationalization and confiscation. Nevertheless, a number of scientists disagree with this understanding of expropriation: some scholars note that expropriation is the exclusively paid (compensatory) acquisition of an object, another group notes the unpaid nature of expropriation, and some believe that expropriation is solely the acquisition of property (sometimes-only estates and real property located on them) for public purposes that are not related to emergencies. Presumably, this situation arose primarily because of the lack of a single international legal terminology in this sphere. Thus, we can find similar definitions of expropriation in foreign countries: "eminent domain" (United States of America, Philippines), "compulsory purchase" (Great Britain, New Zealand, Ireland), "resumption" (Hong Kong), "resumption/compulsory acquisition" (Australia), "expropriation" (South Africa, Canada), "alienation of land for (state) public needs (public necessity)" (Ukraine, Russia). The CIS countries do not use the term "expropriation" in their legislations (with the exception of the Republic of Moldova-article 94 of the Land Code states that conditions and procedure of expropriation for state or public needs of land and construction objects, owned by physical and legal parties, are regulated by the special legislation), although, these countries often use the studied term within international legal agreements. This also creates additional disagreements in the correct understanding of this institution. Complex international legal documents do not use special terminology (for example, article 1 of the Protocol No. 1 to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950, they only contain a rule that the private owner cannot be deprived of property, except in the public interest. Despite inconsistencies in international legal and national approaches to understanding of expropriation, the unifying factor is that expropriation is understood as the compulsory acquisition specifically of estates (Doupe & Salter, 2000).

A normative rule about the non-discriminatory nature of provisions regulating property of private owners is contained in constitutions of most countries of the world in general forms. More detailed principles and provisions concerning compulsory acquisition of estates and the issue of compensation to owners of acquired estates are defined in separate laws. In foreign countries, compulsory acquisition of estates is regulated by a number of normative-legal acts, based on the following principles: clearly defined public needs or emergencies; the need for just and full reimbursement to the owners of expropriated estates; designation of procedural rights of the parties concerned, including a preliminary notice, the right to just compensation and the right to appeal; court hearing of compensatory offers if there are any procedural violations, abuses, etc. As a rule, these principles and provisions concerning compulsory acquisition of estates and the issue of compensation to owners of acquired estates are defined in separate laws (Anderson, 2014).

The Constitution of the Kingdom of Norway is the oldest one in Europe-adopted back in the early nineteenth century (May 17, 1814), it is still in continuous force, having undergone significant changes in the course of constitutional reforms. However, some of its provisions have been retained from its first edition to this day. Such provisions include § 104, which envisages that the right to immovable and movable property cannot be violated in any way, and § 105, according to which, if for reasons of state necessity any property is to be conceded into public use, the owner receives a full reimbursement from state treasury.

In the Constitution of the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg of 17 October 1868 (as amended), article 16 states:

"No one shall be deprived of their property except in the public interest and in the manner prescribed by law, and subject to fair and prior compensation".

In the 19th century, the theory of the social function of property got widespread use in Europe, whose ideas are incorporated in constitutional approaches to regulation of property relations, includes compulsory acquisition of private property. The theory of the social function of property, according to which subjects of property rights are obliged to obey social norms and fulfill social functions assigned to them, was enthusiastically received by western legislators. At the same time, scientists expressed the opinion that elements of such ideas were usually included in the constitution, which arose on the wave of popular speeches and resolutions.

One of the first European constitutions that incorporated a new approach to the recognition of the social function of private property was Germany's Weimar Constitution of 1919. It established private property as "social duty". Compulsory acquisition of property was allowed only for the needs of society, on legal grounds and for an appropriate reimbursement (Fox, 2000).

Of particular interest is France, whose legal development is historically linked to the beginning of the formation of its institutions. The Declaration of the French Republic of 4 October 1788 reserves attention to a crime committed by a convicted person (objects of crime, instruments and means of committing a crime, property obtained through crime, dangerous or harmful objects, etc.), executed by a special law and to the benefit of a state. Punishment in the form of special confiscation of property is covered in legislations of such countries as the Republic of Korea, the Netherlands, Japan, etc. The third group of states has two types of confiscation-established-general and special. Such countries include, in particular, France and Ukraine.

It is worth noting that some countries have fully or partially abandoned such an institute of criminal law as confiscation of property. A number of countries have placed a prohibition on the application of general confiscation in their constitutions (Azerbaijan, Argentina, Barbados, Bahrain, Belgium, Cyprus, Colombia, Costa Rica, Lebanon, Malaysia, Maldives, Mexico, Nicaragua, UAE, Paraguay, Romania, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Chile, etc.) Such prohibition is justified by the fact that confiscation of property results in almost complete material insecurity not only for the convict but also their family, a substantial psychological impact on these individuals, which do not correspond with the goals of punishment. In addition, such measures violate the rights and freedoms of citizens and are an obstacle to humanization and liberalization of criminal law. The legislation of the Republic of Georgia recognizes any confiscation of property as an anti-constitutional norm and is excluded from provisions of the Criminal Code because of violation of the principle of obligatory equivalent compensation for the acquisition of private property.

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